

CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF PROCEDURAL SAFEGUARDS OF EMPLOYMENT RELATED INTERESTS OF THE CIVIL SERVANTS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Civil Servant is indispensable to the governance of the country in the modern administrative age. The civil services form an integral part and play crucial role in any modern democratic Government. In a democracy, the policy of the administration is determined and laid down by political executives (the minister) but the policy is carried out and the administration is largely run by permanent executives (The civil servants). The civil services, in fact, form the backbone of the whole administrative set-up in democracy. The civil servants are almost entirely recruited through open competitive examinations. It was the Chinese who gave the world the concept of recruitment of civil service through an open competitive examination.

Civil services being the back bone of administration have to bear a lot of stress. There is always a demand to perform, pressure of superior official, frivolous complaints, unnecessary departmental proceedings etc. At the same time a lack of working environment, independence to execute the assigned duty add to the misery of the civil servants. A lot of sub-ordinate honest officer and staff fall under the caprice and prey of dishonest and corrupt superior officers inflicting wrong allegations and charges for not being agree with corrupt practices or not to agree to work dishonestly. Thus, they have to face harassment and arbitrary action of superior authority by way of framing of charges with malafide intention, by way of drawing departmental proceedings, disciplinary action like suspension, dismissal, reduction in rank, holding up of salary, increment etc. with fabricated, false and concocted charges till he takes the path of corruption is really disturbing. The procedural safeguards afforded protection to some extent but not against the officials who with malafide intentions frame the charges against the civil servants. Battle before the court is also a long drawn journey which adds to the desolation of honest civil servants. Unnecessary departmental enquiries, suspension with malafide intention, disciplinary actions reduce the efficiency of the civil servants and their interest in office work and ultimately affect good governance.

Thus in this backdrop the current research endeavor is entitled to study the “Conceptual analysis of procedural safeguards of employment related interests of the civil servants in India.”

Key Words: Civil services, Government Employee, India, Procedural safeguards.

INTRODUCTION

In a democracy public services has a crucial role to play. A perusal of the history of the British Empire reveals that among its greatest achievements are the development of the parliamentary institutions and the organization of the Civil Service which is unconnected with party politics and uncontaminated by selfish interest. Their first duty is to give their undivided allegiance to the state at all times and on all occasions. The political horizon at all times may be full of uncertainties and vicissitudes caused by political rivalries or like factors but due to civil servants these impediments are unable to dismantle the normal life of nation.

The performance of a civil servant depends, to a large extent, on the nature of his conditions of service. He has to be afforded protection in the bonafide discharge of his constitutional duties. It is, therefore, essential to afford to civil servants, judicious, rationalised and adequate protection against arbitrary administrative and punitive action. Article 311 (2) of the Constitution provides for the mandatory procedural safeguards as a condition precedent for imposition of major penalties, subject to certain exceptions as incorporated in the provisos to Article 311(2). But, the denial of the rights of the civil servants have brought forth a whole corpus of law laid by the judiciary which is based on importing the rights, justice and according fairness to the civil servants.

The constitutional amendments effected so far, and interpretations, given by the Supreme Court, have evolved certain principles of judge made law of far reaching importance. Consequently, the Government under certain circumstances can dispense with the services of a civil servant, without holding any enquiry against him in the event of any allegation made against him, on the ground of public policy and public good. This has resulted in a lot of confusion and feeling of uncertainty in the mind-set of civil servants, while delinquent civil servants should be dealt with strictly, honest and dedicated civil servants should not be made to suffer unnecessarily.

The protective safe guards given under Article 311 are applicable only to civil servants, i.e. public officers. They are not available to defense personnel. In *State of U. P. v A. N. Singh* the Supreme Court has held that a person holds a civil post if there exist a relationship of master and servant between the State and the person holding the post. The relationship is established if the State has right to select and appoint the holder of the post, right to control the manner and method of his doing the work and the payment by it of his wages or remuneration.

There are safeguards under other laws such as Criminal Procedure Code, Service Rules, Commission of Inquiry Act, adjudication through administrative tribunals etc. for the protection of employment related interest of civil servants against the arbitrariness and abuse of process.

The scope of the present study encompasses the constitutional, statutory and procedural protections conferred upon the civil servants for the efficient administration of the government. The efficient administration of the government and successful execution of governmental programs, schemes and policies are dependent upon the civil servants of Union of India as well as the servants of the State. Further this study intends to analyze and encompasses the adjudication of dispute and complaints in respect of recruitment and some important areas pertaining to conditions of services of persons appointed to civil services and post in connections with the affairs of the State by the Apex Court and the administrative tribunals established under law.

Hence the present research is aimed at knowing and analyzing the protections conferred upon the civil servants, some conditions of service of civil servants of India, and also the role of judiciary and Administrative tribunals to protect and safeguard the interest of civil servants.

OBJECTIVES OF RESERCAH STUDY

Therefore the main objectives of this research are;

1. To analyze the Constitutional Protections given to the Civil Servants
2. To analyze the Judicial Outlook on Procedural Safeguards to the Civil Servants .

HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

For the purpose, the investigator had examined the following hypothesis:

Constitutional and Legislative provisions for the protection of the civil servants need to be strengthened.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

No protections were provided to the civil servants during the Hindu and Mughal period, though the civil servants were in need of protections against the arbitrary actions of terminating the services of the civil servants. The civil servants during the colonial era were discharging their duties at the will of the employer.

During the British period the first time protections are provided to the civil servants by way of providing protections in respect of removal and dismissal of the civil servant under the Government of India Act 1919. Further the scope of the protections is enhanced under the Government of India Act. 1935. The protections provided under the Government of India Acts 1919 and 1935 created the history of providing the protections to the civil servants during British era in India.

Though the civil servants were in need of protections prior to the Government of India 1919 and 1935, the East India Company was not willing to provide the protections to the civil servants, because, if the protections are provided to the civil servants it was difficult for them to exercise the absolute control over the administration. The Directors of the East India Company knows that it will be difficult for them to exercise control if the rights are conferred upon the civil servants.

The study has proved that even after the coming in the force of Indian Constitution there is no much development on statutory protections to the civil servants, though Article 309 of the Constitution of India confers powers upon the parliament of India to make law on the service matters like recruitment and conditions of services of civil servants. At present the recruitment and conditions of services of civil servants in India are governed by the Rules but not by the Statute.

Equality of treatment of civil servants is the basis concept of the welfare state. In that direction the Constitution of India provided certain protections to protect the civil servants against the arbitrary acts of the Government in not providing the equal treatment of all the civil servants. The mere incorporation of the provision under the Constitution is not sufficient to attain the

equality of treatment of all the civil servants. The parliament of India should enact law for the purpose of providing equal treatment to all the civil servants who are discharging their valuable duties and responsibilities towards the satisfactions of the public. As in United Kingdom statutory protections are provided to the civil servants in relation to the equality of employment in public service under the Equality Act 2010 and in United States of America title VII of the Civil Rights Act 1964 provided the Equality of employment in public service.

For the purpose of achieving equality in public employment the Constitutional law also provided provisions regarding reservation in public employment to the backward class of the citizen. Unfortunately no law has been enacted to define who are the persons comes under the category of the backward class, the extent of reservation is to be provided, and who are not eligible to enjoy the benefit of reservation. Fortunately the Supreme Court of India as a protector and the guardian of the Indian Constitution interpreted the provisions of the reservation by laying down the ratio in number of judgment's with the object of the achieving the philosophy of the founding father of the Constitution.

The study has proved that as compared to the statutory protections provided to the civil servants of the United Kingdom and United States America, protections provided under the constitutional law are inadequate and devoid of enforceability of constitutional protections provided to the civil servants in India.

The most notable finding of the research is that, the role of judiciary and the Administrative Tribunals in India playing an immense role in protecting the rights of the civil servants to discharge their duties and responsibilities without any fear or favour towards the satisfaction of the public. The civil servants are vested with innumerable functions to be discharged without any fear or favour and while doing their duties strictly according to the law may be subject to ill treatment, humiliation and even some circumstances are subject to suspension, transfer, compulsory termination, removal or even dismissal without following the rules. Therefore the Apex Court and Administrative Tribunals Constituted under the Administrative Tribunals Act 1985 playing commendable job to protect the interest of the honest civil servants.

Another important notable findings of the researcher is that the intension of 42nd Amendment to the Constitution has partially defeated in view of the decision of the Supreme Court of India in L. Chandrakumar's case, a seven judges Bench of the Supreme Court, while declaring the power of judicial review as in essential and basic feature of the Constitution, extended the power even to the Administrative Tribunals established under the Administrative Tribunals Act. 1985. The Supreme Court held that the Administrative Tribunals are competent to hear the service matters where the vires of statutory provisions are questioned with a rider, however, that Administrative Tribunals cannot act as substitute for the High Courts and Supreme Court which have been specifically entrusted with such an obligation under the Constitution. In view of the law lay

down by the Supreme Court that all such decisions of the Administrative Tribunals will be subject to scrutiny before a division bench of the respective High Courts.

The researcher in the course of research found that equality of treatment in public employment is the common protection to civil servants in India, United Kingdom and United States of America. Further the reservation policy has been introduced in India to protect the interest of backward class by providing special treatment to attain the objectives of equality under the Constitution, protected Characteristics has been added to protect the protected characteristics in United Kingdom and affirmative action programs are introduced in United State of America. The protections provided to the civil servants India are Constitutional protections whereas the protections provided to the civil servants of United Kingdom and United States of America is Statutory in nature.

The service conditions of the civil servants of the states are concerned; the civil servants in India are governed by the Rules whereas the Servants of the United Kingdom and United States of America are governed by the Statute. Therefore the Statutory protections are provided to the servants of UK and USA, no such statutory protections are provided in India.

These findings were drawn on the basis of the research and the hypothesis was put on the test to drive at the appropriate conclusions.

CONCLUSION:

The necessity of protecting the civil servants from the arbitrary acts of the political heads and from the executive heads always has been felt throughout the history.

During the time of East India Company, the civil servants held their office at the pleasure of the employer. The employer i.e., East India Company had a power to terminate services of the civil servants at any time without assigning the reasons. The civil servants had no remedy against the arbitrary dismissal or removal from the service.

The East India Company's rule come to an end and the Government of India Act 1858, however did not bring about the any much changes in the position of the civil servants. After the assumption of the control by the Crown over the Indian possessions, the Secretary of State-in-Council was conferred power in relation to the civil services of the state. The Judicial decisions at this stage clearly indicate that the power of the Crown to dismiss or remove the civil servants was absolute. However the Government of India adopted the resolution in 1879 providing for certain procedural protections before the servants could be dismissed or removed from the service. But the resolution has not been implemented and the officials were not given the benefit of the resolution.

It was thought expedient that some restrictions on the 'Doctrine of Pleasure' should be introduced with a view of infusing a sense of security in the minds of the European Civil Servants serving under the Crown in India. As a result the Government of India Act 1919 was passed.

The Government of India Act-1919 was the first enactment to apply the 'doctrine of pleasure' in India, through Section 96B. Its application was "subject to rules" and the courts while examining

challenges to penalties under that Act applied the extant rules to determine whether these were rightly imposed. In other words, when this doctrine was first applied in India, it was deemed sufficient to provide protection against any unjust exercise of pleasure'. The courts enforced these statutory safeguards and it shows the sign of imposing the limitation on the Doctrine of Pleasure were witnessed. Further the Government of India Act 1919 also empowered the Government to make the rules governing the recruitment and conditions of the civil servants. Consequently rules were laid down for removal or dismissal of civil servants. The Government of India Act, 1935 is an important law provided protections to the civil servants. Section 240 of the Act, retain the 'doctrine of pleasure' and at the same time placed restriction upon the doctrine of pleasure. The important safeguards provided under the Government of India Act are;

- (i) a civil servant could not be dismissed by an authority subordinate to that by which he was appointed;
- (ii) No civil servant could be dismissed or reduced in rank until he had been given a reasonable opportunity to show cause against the action proposed to be taken against him subject to exceptions.

The second safeguard was, however made subject two exceptions namely;

- (a) To a person who had been convicted of a criminal charge, and
- (b) If the authority empowered to dismiss or remove the civil servants was satisfied that for some reason, to be recorded in writing, it was not reasonably practicable to give to that person an opportunity of showing cause.

Therefore the Doctrine of Pleasure was made subject to certain statutory limitations as conferred under the Government of India Act, 1919 and the Government of India Act 1935.

Further the need of providing the protections to the civil servants were considered in the Constituent Assembly and the task of laying down the preliminary relating to the constitution was entrusted to Shri B.N. Rau, but preliminary draft do not contain the provisions relation to the protections to the civil servants.

The Drafting Committee framed the new draft and the regulations for the safeguards of civil servants were first time laid down in the draft. The safeguards which were incorporated in the drafts were taken from the Government of India Act 1935. The safeguards provided for the infliction of major penalty only after providing a reasonable opportunity to the civil servant. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel highlighted the importance of civil service and incorporation of the basic guarantee to the civil servants in the Constitution itself. Finally the draft was placed before the constituent Assembly for discussion by Dr B.R.Ambedkar.

During the elaborate valuable discussion on providing protection to the civil servants in the Constituent Assembly, the members of the Constituent Assembly suggests many amendments and finally after discussion draft Article 282-B was adopted. At the revision stage the Article on the services were renumbered as Article 308 to 314. Article 310 of the Constitution of India

embedded the Doctrine of Pleasure and Article 311(1) and (2) of the Constitution provides for the safeguards against the dismissal, removal and reduction of rank of civil servants serving under the Union and the State.

The Constitution of India reposes great trust and confidence in the civil services and gives the civil servants a security of tenure and conditions of service and in turn expects an honest and sincere service from the members of the civil services for providing to the peoples of India an efficient, honest, polite and incorruptible administration. It is the duty of every person appointed to the any post under the Union or the State to discharge his duties and responsibilities according to the expectations of the Constitution and befitting the trust and confidence reposed in the civil servants of the State by the Constitution.

Security of employment is the basic element of good and efficient administration. With a view of providing security of employment to the civil servants the framers of the Indian Constitution provided adequate safeguards to the civil servant to discharge their duties and responsibilities towards the satisfaction of the public. The doctrine of pleasure has been incorporated in Article 310 of the Constitution of India. The power of the President or the Governors of the State to remove, dismiss and reduction in rank of the civil servants of the State under Article 310 of the Constitution is not absolute and is subject to Article 311 and the fundamental rights. Unlike the Doctrine of Pleasure in United Kingdom wherein the power of the Crown is absolute in terminating the service of the civil servants, whereas in India the Doctrine of Pleasure though modeled on the British pattern is not absolute and unfettered.

The Constitutional law itself guaranteed the certain protections against the power of dismissal, removal, and reduction of rank under Article 311 of the Constitution. Article 311(1) of the Constitution guarantees that the appointing authority has the power to remove or dismiss the civil servant. Further as per the law laid down by the Supreme Court and various High Courts not only the appointing authority but also an authority equal in rank or superior to the appointing authority may dismiss or remove the civil servant. Therefore Article 311(1) of the Constitution is the fetter upon the authority to exercise arbitrary act of dismissal or removal of civil servants of the State.

Another most important protection provided to the civil servants of the State under Article 311(2) of the Constitution of India is reasonable opportunity to defend before passing an order of removal, dismissal or reduction in rank. The expression “reasonable” is not susceptible of clear and precise definition.

The term reasonable does not mean the best; it means the most suitable in a given set of circumstance. The far reaching decision of the Supreme Court of India in *Khemchand V. Union of India* laid down the scope and the meaning of the expression of “reasonable opportunity” viz., an opportunity to deny his guilt and to establish his innocence, an opportunity to defend himself by cross examining the witnesses produced against the servant and an opportunity to make his representation as to why the proposed punishment should not be inflicted on him.

The 15th Amendment and 42nd Amendment to the Article 311(2) of the Constitution tries to mitigate the protections conferred upon the civil servants of the State, but still the protection under Article 311(2) remained in view of the decision of the Supreme Court of India in various cases because of its importance in protecting the interest of honest, impartial and unbiased civil servants against the arbitrary exercise of power by the higher authority who are having the power to take action against the civil servants.

With the provisions of Judicial review now available in our Constitution, the protection available to Government employees is indeed formidable even outside Article 311. This is borne out by the fact that ample relief is available to employees invoking judicial intervention in cases involving compulsory retirements even though Article 311 does not extend to such cases.

When Sardar Vallabhai Patel argued in the constituent Assembly for protection of civil servants and for the establishment of the All India Service, the intention was clearly to embolden senior civil servants to render impartial and frank advice to the political executive without any kind of fear of taking action against the Civil Servants. But these protections have created a climate of excessive security to the corrupt civil servants of the State, without fear of penalty for incompetence or wrongdoing; on the other hand these protections are acting as a steal frame to the honest, impartial and unbiased civil servants of the State. The challenge before the nation now is to confront this exaggerated notion of lifetime security irrespective of performance and to create a climate conducive to effective delivery of services and accountability with reasonable security of tenure to the corrupt civil servants.

The rights of a civil servant under the Constitution should be subordinate to the overall requirement of public interest and the contractual right of the State. It cannot be an argument that a corrupt civil servant's rights are more important than the need to ensure an honest, efficient and corruption free Administration. Ultimately, the public servant, an agent of the State, cannot be superior to the State and it is his fundamental duty to serve the State with integrity, devotion, honesty, impartiality, objectivity, transparency and accountability. It is true that the government as an employer is expected to act in a fair manner and it has to be a model employer worthy of emulation by others. It has also to be ensured that honest and efficient public servants are not subjected to the whims and fancies of their superiors. Articles 309, 310 and 311 form a continuum. If the whole gamut of "conditions of service" is codified as required by the substantive part of Article 309, this can include matters such as disciplinary proceedings and imposition of penalties. Moreover, the rule of law accepted as an integral part of the basic structure of the constitution, reasonable protection now attributed to Article 311 will continue to be available to satisfy the requirements of 'rule of law'. Taking into account these considerations and a fairly common perception that explicit articulation of "protection" in the Constitution itself gives an impression of inordinate "protection", the Administrative Reforms Commission is of the view that on balance Article 311 need not continue to be a part of the Constitution. Instead appropriate and comprehensive legislation under Article 309 could be framed to cover all aspects of recruitment and service, even with regard to dismissal, removal or reduction in rank. Appropriate legislation by the respective legislatures may also be ensured through a revised Constitutional provision.

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Further the Constitutional law of India confers the protection of equality of treatment in matters relating to employment to all the citizens and prohibits discrimination on the grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, descent, place of birth, residence or any of them. However to attain the equality, economic and social, the Constitutional law confers reservation to the socially, economically and educationally backward classes in relation to the employment and education. Certain protections are also conferred to the permanent civil servants of the State under the Code of Criminal procedure, Prevention of Corruption Act and the Code of Civil procedure in relation to the prosecution of civil servants, procedural protection and in relation to the civil suits.

More importantly the constitutional law confers v importantly the constitutional law confers very important protections are provided to the civil servant of the Union as well as the State under Article 311(1) and (2) of the Constitution. In a democratic country where in the civil servants has to work under the political heads are always facing the threat of suspension, transfer or even illegal removal from the service. The honest, impartial and unbiased civil servants becomes the victims of the political decisions of premature transfers from place to place without any fault of civil servants and even becomes the victims of initiating disciplinary enquiry at the instance of the ministers. Therefore the constitutional of India guaranteed the most notable protections to the civil servant in its Article 311(1) and 311(2). The Supreme Court of India and the High Courts in its land mark judgment's further protected the protections guaranteed to the honest and impartial civil servants.

Therefore the researcher concluded on the basis of the study conducted in the course of research that “No other Constitution in the world appears to contain these kind protections, than the constitutional law of India confers the protections to the permanent Civil servants of the State.” But these protections provided under the Constitutional law are not adequate to meet the requirement of the civil servants and need to enact the laws for the protection of the civil servants who are considered as the back bone of the Indian Administration.

SUGGESTIONS

- The first suggestion which the researcher is to make is the definition of the term Civil Servant or the Civil Post has to made it clear by defining the terms in the service laws. In the absence of the clear definition of the terms leads to confusion in the minds of the servants as to whether they are the civil servants or not and the protections provided under the Constitutional law of India are applicable or not.

- Separate Law for reducing the inequality by enacting law governing the equality in employment in civil service. As we are well aware that unless, the provisions of the Constitution has been implemented through the enactment, it is not possible to achieve the objectives of the Constitution. The Constitutional law guarantees the right to equality in public employment under Article 16 with certain exceptions to attain the equality, but so far no law has been enacted to implement the guarantees as provide under the Constitutional Law. Therefore the researcher suggested enacting separate law to implement the law relating to equality in public employment as enacted in United Kingdom.
- With a view to bringing about uniformity and consistency in the service rules, the adhoc rules, as framed by the executive should be replaced by statutory rules under Article 309 of the Constitution.
- In the interest of the probationary employees, the service rules should provide for a maximum permissible limit of probation, instead of permitting extension of probationary periods for an indefinite period. The objective is to check possible abuse of service conditions of probationers by the departmental authorities.
- Article 310 (1) of the Constitution should be amended so as to provide for judicial review of the 'Doctrine of Pleasure' to the defense service personnel, in order to check.
- It necessary to establish Statutory Commission and Tribunal to implement equal employment law and to overcome the violation of equal employment opportunity. Like in the United States of America the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) guarantee the equal employment opportunity and provides the well-defines investigating mechanism in case of violation of equal employment opportunity any malafide exercise of power by the departmental authorities.
- The scope of the second opportunity of showing cause, as provided in Article 311 (2) prior to the forty second constitutional amendment needs to be restored. The scope of second opportunity which was snapped needs to be restored by way of suitable amendment, so as to provide for a reasonable time limit within which the second opportunity of showing cause may be availed by the civil servant.
- Many a civil service litigation has been occasioned as the consequence of faulty enquiries. Therefore, it should be made incumbent on the departmental authorities to entrust enquiries to officials possessing a legal background. This mechanism would enable an enquiry officer to make a fair appreciation of the evidence on record and ensure the enquiry officer's adherence to proper procedures.
- In enquiries involving technical issues or the interpretation of law, or in a case, where the aggrieved civil servant has to face a legally trained mind during the course of the enquiry, the civil servant should be allowed the assistance of a lawyer.

- To remove socio-economic inequality need to enact comprehensive legislation on providing the protection to those who have not sufficiently represented in the public employment

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